

A Prospective Observational Screening Assessment of Carcinoma of Cervix Using Pap Smear

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Aim: The aim of the present study was to evaluate the pattern of cervical Pap smear cytology at a tertiary hospital in Bihar region and to correlate it with clinical findings.

Methods: This prospective study was carried out over 1 year in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology in Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India. We screened 200 women were included in the study.

Results: Maximum number of cases was in the age group 30-39 years constituting 35% of the total cases followed by age group 20-29 years 30%. Minimum percentage (1.5%) of cases were under 60-69 and 70-79 age group. Vaginal discharge was the commonest chief complaint followed by menorrhagia and lower abdominal pain. Maximum number of cases reported as Non-Specific Inflammatory Smears (55%). Among epithelial cell abnormalities incidence of ASCUS, SCC and ASCUS – H was 1%.

Conclusion: This study emphasized the importance of Pap smears screening for early detection of premalignant and malignant lesions of cervix. Pap smear testing is an economical, non-invasive and simple OPD procedure to detect potentially precancerous and cancerous lesions of cervix. It should be established as a routine screening procedure to reduce the treatment burden, morbidity and mortality.

Keywords: Cervical Malignancy, HPV DNA Testing, Pap Smear.

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Introduction

Cervical cancer is an increasing health problem, comprising approximately 12% of all cancers among women worldwide. [1] According to the world cancer statistics, developing and low resource countries have more than 80% of all the cervical cancers due to lack of awareness and difficulty in running cytology-based screening programmes. [2] India has the highest age standardized incidence of

cervical cancers in South Asia. [3] By simple pap screening test cervical cancer and its precursor lesions can be detected and treated early. Pap smear is a routine screening test with sensitivity of 70- 80% in detecting HSIL. [4] Usually Pap smear screening test is recommended starting around 21 years of age upto 65 years. Repeated examination is recommended after every three years interval and in case

of abnormal Pap smear report follow up is advisable six monthly. [5]

Cancer of cervix is readily preventable, by early detection and appropriate timely treatment of its precursor lesions by simple Pap screening test. But, women usually present to the clinic only when they have symptoms, such as pain, discharge, and/or abnormal bleeding. [6] Cervical epithelial cell abnormalities in the Pap smear represents a spectrum of intraepithelial lesions that lie along the pathway, from mild-to-severe dysplasia to invasive cancer. [7] Though Pap smear is a routine screening test, the overall sensitivity in detection of high grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (HSIL) is 70 -80%. [8] The Bethesda System (TBS) for reporting the results of cervical cytology was developed as a uniform system of terminology that could provide clear guidance for clinical management.

Cervical cancer is a preventable disease due to the long preinvasive stage. Early detection and appropriate treatment are possible if robust screening is implemented. [9] Early cervical epithelial changes can be identified by a Pap smear test, which is the primary screening test for detection of precancerous cervical intraepithelial neoplasia and the early stage of invasive cervical cancer. Due to widespread screening programs, there has been a significant reduction in mortality from cervical cancer in developed countries. The overall sensitivity of the Pap test in detecting a high-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (HSIL) is 70.80%. [10] A Pap screening done in association with an HPV DNA test increases the sensitivity for early detection of precancerous lesions. [11] There is a need to spread cervical cancer screening awareness programs, educate women regarding the symptoms of cancer, and motivate them to visit the hospital for a cancer screening. Women and all family members should be counseled about the need for cancer screening. Pap smear-

positive women need adequate treatment and regular follow-up.

The aim of the present study was to evaluate the pattern of cervical Pap smear cytology at a tertiary hospital and to correlate it with clinical findings.

Materials and Methods

This prospective study was carried out over 1 year in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology in Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India. We screened 200 women were included in the study.

Women with different complaints, including vaginal discharge, blood-mixed discharge, foul-smelling discharge, postcoital bleeding, intermenstrual bleeding, postmenopausal bleeding, abdominal pain, infertility, and secondary amenorrhea, were included in this study. Those not willing to participate in the study had a frank growth, had been treated for cervical cancer, or were pregnant were excluded from the study. A detailed history was taken using a predetermined proforma that included the chief complaint and the findings of per speculum and vaginal examinations. Written informed consent was obtained from all women. Patients were placed in the lithotomy position, and a sterile bivalve speculum was inserted into the vagina. The posterior vaginal wall was retracted posteriorly and the anterior vaginal wall anteriorly to allow proper visualization of the cervix and vaginal wall.

A sample was taken from the ectocervix by rotating a wooden Ayre spatula 360°. The sample was quickly smeared onto a labeled glass slide and fixed with 95% ethyl alcohol in a jar. The glass slides were sent to the Department of Pathology for cytopathological examination. Laboratory results were reported according to the new Bethesda System for Reporting Cervical Cytology 2014. The system broadly divides lesions into those negative for

intraepithelial neoplasia and epithelial cell abnormalities (ECA) that include squamous and glandular cells. Women who had abnormal Pap test results, including atypical squamous cells of undetermined significance (ASCUS), low-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (LSIL), and HSIL were sent for a

colposcopic examination. Women who had an abnormal colposcopic finding, i.e., a Reid score 6 or above, underwent a colposcopy-guided biopsy. Treatment was provided according to the stage of the disease.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of Cases according to age

Age groups	N	%
20-29	60	30
30-39	70	35
40-49	40	20
50-59	24	12
60-69	3	1.5
70-79	3	1.5
Total	200	100

Maximum number of cases was in the age group 30-39 years constituting 35% of the total cases followed by age group 20-29 years 30%. Minimum percentage (1.5%) of cases were under 60-69 and 70-79 age group.

Table 2: Distribution of cases according to symptoms

Symptoms	N	%
Asymptomatic	10	5
Vaginal Discharge	80	40
Pain lower abdomen	40	20
Menorrhagia	30	15
Post- Coital Bleeding	16	8
Post- menopausal Bleeding	12	6
Something coming out of vagina	8	4
Burning Micturation	4	2
Total	200	100

Vaginal discharge was the commonest chief complaint followed by menorrhagia and lower abdominal pain.

Table 3: Spectrum of diseases on pap smear

Diseases	N	%
Unsatisfactory	4	2
Normal	4	2
Inflammatory (Non-specific)	110	55
Trichomoniasis	14	7
Candidiasis	18	9
Bacterial Vaginosis	18	9
Mixed infections		
Candida + T. Vaginalis	3	
Candida + Bacterial Vaginosis	2	3
T. Vaginalis+ B. Vaginosis	1	

Actinomycosis	2	1
ASCUS	2	1
ASCUS- H	2	1
SCC	2	1
Atrophic	18	9
Total	200	100

Maximum number of cases reported as Non- Specific Inflammatory Smears (55%). Among epithelial cell abnormalities incidence of ASCUS, SCC and ASCUS – H was 1%.

Discussion

Cancers of uterine cervix and breast are the leading malignancies seen in females of India. There should be an effective mass screening program aimed at specific age group for detecting precancerous condition before they progress to invasive cancers. [12,13] Cervical cytology is currently widely used as the most effective cancer screening modality. Objective data from hospital-based studies are required in order to detect the efficiency of the screening test.

In the present study, most of the abnormal cytology was detected in patients in the age group between 30 and 60 years. Gupta et al. [14] reported that most of the abnormal cytology cases, i.e., 40.37%, in their study were in the age group of 30–39 years, followed by 35.96% in the age group of 20–29 years. The commonest presenting complaint of females was vaginal discharge which was 40% similar to the studies conducted by Verma et al [15], Sunita et al [16], Lakshmi et al [17] and Sachan et al. [18] Menorrhagia and Lower abdominal pain was 16.01% and 15.15% respectively, Post coital bleeding in 8.22%, Post-menopausal bleeding in 6.92%, burning micturition in 4.76%. 4.32% case had complaint of something coming out of vagina while same percentage was asymptomatic.

In our study inflammatory smears constituted the maximum bulk of the reporting (55%) which was almost similar

to the study of Lakshmi et al [17], Sunita et al. [16], Sachan [18] and Verma et al. [15] Incidence of Candidiasis and Bacterial vaginosis was 9.09% in our study. Sunita et al reported candida in 2.50% of the total pap smear studied whereas Laxmi et al [17] diagnosed 3% cases of bacterial vaginosis. ASCUS and ASCUS- H constituted 0.86% each of the total cases in the present study which was in concordance with the study conducted by Verma et al. [15] Incidence of ASCUS was little higher in studies of Sunita et al [16], Lakshmi et al [17] and Sachan et al. [18] One case (0.43%) of SCC was diagnosed in our study which was in concordance to the findings of Sunita [16] and Lakshmi et al. [17] Unsatisfactory for evaluation was reported in 4 cases (1.73%) which was similar to the observations made by Verma et al. [15] Lakshmi et al [17] labelled 4% case as normal smear study, almost similar to the present study. Edelman et al, [19] studied Pap smears from 29295 females over a period of one year and the Pap smear abnormalities were as follows: 9.9% ASC-US, 2.5% LSIL, 0.6% HSIL, and 0.2% invasive cancer. Study by Banik U [20] revealed the following scenario: 0.18% ASCUS, 0.12% Atypical glandular cells (AGC), 6.36% LSIL, 1.18% HSIL and 0.35% malignancy. In our study shows ASCUS 0.77%, ASC-H 0.35%, HSIL 0.35%, SCC 0.14% and AGUS 0.28%. [21]

As we all know that cervical cancer is one of the leading causes of mortality in India and its precursor lesions usually occur 5-10 years earlier. Henceforth, Pap smear examination is an important and fundamental tool for the screening,

prevention and early diagnosis of cervical cancers.

Conclusion

This study emphasized the importance of Pap smears screening for early detection of premalignant and malignant lesions of cervix. Pap smear testing is an economical, non-invasive and simple OPD procedure to detect potentially precancerous and cancerous lesions of cervix. It should be established as a routine screening procedure to reduce the treatment burden, morbidity and mortality. Larger studies are required to estimate the pattern of cervical cytological abnormalities along with detection of common HPV strains in cervical cancer in Indian population. Pap smear examination should begin at 30 years. By proper implementation of Pap screening program, incidence of invasive cervical malignancy can be prevented due to early detection of cervical premalignant lesions.

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